

ISic2718

I.Sicily inscription 2718

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museum or catacomb Antiquarium

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. [---]

1. [---]A,N[---]

2. (vac.unknown)M[---]

3. [---]IEKṬ[---]

3a. [---]

Apparatus

Text after Griesheimer 1996 with slight changes based on the photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645138

PHI 333385

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 46.1289

Griesheimer, M. 1996. Nouvelles inscriptions funéraires de la catacombe Saint-Jean. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 72: 115-132. At 125 no.9 fig.9

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